

Project Overview

The aim of this project is to conduct an impartial comparison between the numerous models which have been developed to examine land-atmosphere exchanges within the urban environment.

The project has commenced with participants being issued a test dataset (VL92) which they are to run and return the output to us. This step is largely to ensure that all parties can communicate. On completion of this first stage, participating groups will be provided increasingly detailed climate data from an urban region over four stages (Table 1). The precise location of this region will be unknown to participants. Models are to be run offline using this data and participants are to return the corresponding **output** and **model parameters** to us for comparison.

We currently have approximately 40 modelling groups participating (Table 2 provides details of these). Despite this large number, we would still like to hear from any other parties who might be interested. If you are interested, please contact us at: UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk.

Table 1: Planned timetable

Target date	Objective
1 March [†]	Outputs of test data returned
1 April	First dataset released*
1 May	Second dataset released*
1 June	Third dataset released*

[†] It is important that all groups successfully run the specimen data set. If you have not completed this please let us know when you hope to get this to us date.

* Note: subsequent datasets will only be released following our receipt of output from the previous step.

Current Status

- Table 2 lists the participants to date and the progress so far with respect to the first pre-test stage. A number of groups have also requested to join the project recently.

- All participants have been provided with an initial questionnaire document requesting information concerning the model(s) they will run.
- Those who have returned the questionnaire have been provided with the pre-test dataset (VL92) for initial runs of their models.
- The output data returned by participants have been examined to ensure compatibility for further analysis and/or so that potential errors/inaccuracies can be isolated. Groups returning data with apparent problems have been, or will be, informed as soon as possible.
- Meteorological data from a variety of urban sites has been acquired and is in the process of being analysed for its suitability in this work. Based on the datasets available it is looking increasingly likely that more than one round of evaluation will be possible using data from more than one urban site.
- It is planned that initial results from the first stage of this work will be available for presentation at the AMS Annual Meeting in January 2009. Depending on interest, we may consider requesting a specific session at this meeting. Abstracts are due August 1st. Please note that the annual meeting will have an urban theme. Later in the year we will ask you to let us know if you would be interested in participating in such a session. It is hoped that the presentation of final results for Round 1 will be at the IAUC 7 Meeting in June 2009.
- A summary of the project aims and rationale has been submitted for inclusion in the next issue of the IAUC newsletter, so as to raise awareness of the project.
- For information to participants, a set of FAQs can be found at the end of this newsletter. If this document fails to answer any queries you may have then please contact us at the email address given.

Parameter values: If you have not already done so, please return the parameter values assigned when running the VL92 dataset.

Latitude and Longitude: This will not be provided for Round 1. Please can you let us know why you need it. You will be provided with incoming solar radiation

Table 2: Participating Modelling Groups and their current status.

Model	Participant(s)	Received Contact?	Questionnaire tables complete?	Test data sent?	Test data output received at KCL (due: 1 March)	Output satisfactory?	Parameter details returned?
BEP02	Martilli	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
BEP05	Hamdi		✓	✓			
BEP_BEM08	Francisco	✓	✓	✓			
CLMU	Oleson	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
ENVImet	Bruse		✓	✓			
GCTTC	Shashua Bar	✓	✓	✓			
HIRLAM-U	Baklanov		✓	✓			
HPDM-Urban	Steve Hanna	✓†	✓				
LUMPS	Loridan	✓	✓	✓			
MM5u	Dandou; Tombrou	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
JULES	Gouvea	✓	✓	✓			
JULEST	Best	✓	✓	✓			
JULES2T	Best	✓	✓	✓			
JULES-U	Porson	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
MUCM	Kondo	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
MUKLIMO	Sievers		✓	✓			
Noah-LSM	Loridan	✓	✓	✓			
NJU-UCM-S	Zhang	✓	✓	✓			
NJU-UCM-M	Zhang	✓	✓	✓			
NSLUCM	Miao; Chen	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
RUM2	Bohnenstengel	✓	✓	✓			
RUM4	Bohnenstengel	✓	✓	✓			
SEB	Pearlmutter	✓					
SLUCM	Kusaka	✓	✓	✓			
SM2U	Calmet	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
SUEB	Fortuniak		✓	✓			
SUMM	Kanda		✓	✓			
SUNBEEM	Arnfield	✓	✓	✓			
TEB	Pigeon; Masson	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
TEB	Mailhot	✓†					
TEB07	Hamdi	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
TUF2D	Krayenhoff; Voogt	✓	✓	✓			
TUF3D	Krayenhoff; Voogt	✓	✓	✓			
UCLM	Mills		✓	✓			
UCM (modified)	Song; Ma	✓					
VUCM	Lee; Baik	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
1D-MSD	Khosla	✓					
-	Taha	✓†					
-	Brown						
-	Srivastav	✓					

† lack of resource to participate in first round

Urban Model Comparison FAQs

What is this project about?

Please see the documents at:

http://www.kcl.ac.uk/ip/suegrimmond/model_comparison.htm

What are the first steps required to join the model comparison?

1. Contact us at: UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk.
2. Complete the questionnaire tables in relation to the model you will run. If using multiple models please complete for each.
3. We will send you a test data set (VL92). Please run this and send back your model output.
4. Once we have determined that it is compatible you are ready to participate in the formal runs (stages 1-4).

What do the model codes stand for?

Participants have been asked to name their models (usually an acronym). These names are used to describe each model for comparative purposes. When the results are presented anonymous codes will be used: you will only know your code. Models will be referred to by this code following the testing phase.

What time-zone should be assumed?

Please use the time within the test file (i.e. local time).

What are averaging periods for the data?

The data are hourly average values for the hour ending. i.e. 10:00 is 09:01 to 10:00. Your data should be hourly averaged for this time period and not a sample/instantaneous value on the hour.

What are the temporal and spatial scales to be modelled?

Spatial: the model output should be for a point that is at the equivalent of the first layer in a meso-scale model or at the blending height. i.e. it is local scale (spatially integrated for a neighbourhood) as are the observations. It should not be a microscale result for a point within the canyon.

Temporal: The model results will be compared at an hourly time scale. These will be the average for the hour and given the hour ending time stamp.

Where can I get the test data from?

Please email us: UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk The test file is available in either the netCDF or ASCII formats. Please let us know which you would prefer.

Should all variables in the test data be used?

Not necessarily – if your model does not need all the data then do not use it. Please however, use data for the whole time period detailed.

I cannot read the test data

If this happens, it may be that you are examining either the netCDF or ASCII file believing it to be the other. If you are still unable to view the data then please email and we will endeavour to help you.

What does the test data consist of?

The content of the test file (VL92) consists of the following variables:

Day – day (Day of year format from 223 – 238)

Hour – hour (24-hour format)

DecTime - decimal time

Q* - net all wave radiation ($W m^{-2}$)[†]

Qh - turbulent sensible heat flux ($W m^{-2}$)[†]

Qe - turbulent Latent heat flux ($W m^{-2}$)[†]

deltaQs - net storage heat flux ($W m^{-2}$)[†]

WS - wind speed ($m s^{-1}$)

RH - relative Humidity (%)

Tair – air temperature (K)

WindDir – wind direction (°)

Psurf – pressure (Pa)

Rainf – rainfall ($kg m^{-2} s^{-1}$)

SoilTemp – soil temperature (K)

SWDown - incoming shortwave radiation ($W m^{-2}$)

LWDown - incoming longwave radiation ($W m^{-2}$)

[†]these are what should be returned as model outputs (minimum).

These variables meet the ALMA conventions on naming and units where possible although where this is not possible, new naming conventions have been adopted (ie. Day, Hour, DecTime, Q*, deltaQs, WS, RH and WindDir).

What more can we know about the VL92 data?

The site for this test data is Vancouver Light Industrial site (VL92). If you want to obtain

parameters to use in your evaluation these may be available in the following publications:

Best M, CSB Grimmond and MG Villani 2006: *Boundary Layer Meteorology*, 118, 503-525, DOI 10.1007/s10546-005-9025-5

Masson V, C.S.B. Grimmond and T.R. Oke. 2002: *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, 41, 1011-26.

Voogt J.A. and C.S.B. Grimmond. 2000: *Journal of Applied Meteorology*, 39, 1679-1699.

These are available at the website:

<http://www.kcl.ac.uk/ip/suegrimmond/news.htm>)

Which VL92 data version should I use?

Please use any version of VL92 which has been made available. If earlier versions are used then handle the gaps in the dataset using your preferred gap-filling method. If the more recent ASCII version is to be used (VL92_ALMA) then the gaps in the dataset have been filled: this dataset can be viewed using any text editor.

What format should the model outputs be returned in?

The following points summarise our requirements:

1. We will accept data in ASCII format, although netCDF files can also be accepted.
2. Please submit a metadata file detailing the format of your data, with your output file.
3. Ideally your output file will be formatted in the same way as the VL92 ASCII file and will use the ALMA conventions (or our specific conventions).
4. Please, if possible, include the input data from the VL92 file in your output file (or as a separate file).
5. Ensure you are comfortable working with the output format you submit to us as we will require you to continue using this format throughout the model comparison work.

Do I need to tell you what parameters I have used in implementing my model?

Yes – this is important, please send these when you return your model data.

What is the timetable of the project?

We would like the test data returned as soon as possible. Once these have all been reviewed we will provide the actual data to participants with the

requirement that model outputs are returned within 1 month. We aim to issue the first set of data on 1 April (see Table 3 for a full time table).

Table 3 Timetable of project.

Data Set:	Round	Stage	Comments
VL92	0	1	Back by 1 March
Mystery	1	1	Data distributed 1 April
		2	Data distributed 1 May
		3	Data distributed 1 June
		4	Data distributed 1 July

What stages does the project consist of?

This project will consist of four stages. At each stage participants will be issued more information about the collection site. The first set of real data will be distributed on 1 April. Following this there will be three monthly issues of data. We aim to complete the first round of tests by the end of July. Please note that these dates are *provisional*. The table below summarises some of the main dates for each stage of the project.

Will I automatically receive the data for each stage?

No – you will only receive data for the following stage on returning to us the output from the previous stage and on our finding the quality of this data satisfactory.

What constitutes satisfactory data?

This means that we are able to access and analyse the data and that included with the data are details of the parameters used when the model was run. Also, the data returned to us should meet the ALMA conventions as closely as possible.

Will there be a second or third round?

It is hoped that there may be a second round of comparison, each using a different set of forcing data. This of course, depends on data availability and on the success of the first round. Importantly, success depends on the commitment of all participants to meet the time-scales set.

Will I be told of the performance of my model?

Yes – individual groups will be informed but only on the status of their particular model. The results for the rest will be blind.

Can I distribute the data I am sent (either the test data or the evaluation data) or use it for another purpose?

No – the data we send you is for use by you on this project only. We ask you to agree to this by participating in this work. Any data we send must also not be exchanged among participants of the project as you may be at a different stage in the project to other participants.

Can others still get involved in the project?

Yes! If you wish to include other models in this comparison exercise or if you know of other potential participants, please let us know.

Where can I find updates on the project?

The following website will be regularly updated with progress on the project:

http://www.kcl.ac.uk/ip/suegrimmond/model_comparison.htm

What if I have more questions?

Please email UrbanMet@kcl.ac.uk with any further queries and we will respond as quickly as possible.

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